

Learning to LIVE again: The journey of suicide attempt survivors towards recovery and relapse prevention

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Suicide is a complex global public health issue, claiming 703,000 lives annually. For every suicide, numerous individuals attempt to take their own lives, with many cases going unreported. While research on suicide is extensive, much of it focuses on suicidality or the grief of those left behind, leaving a gap in understanding the recovery and relapse prevention of suicide attempt survivors. This study addresses this gap by exploring the lived experiences of individuals recovering from suicide attempts. Using a descriptive phenomenological approach, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 13 Filipino adults who had attempted suicide at least once and had not reattempted for at least six months. Data were analysed using Colaizzi's (1978) method, revealing the central phenomenon, "Learning to LIVE Again," which comprises four interconnected themes: (1) "Loss of Stability and Control Over Self," (2) "Implications of the Attempt to Self and Others," (3) "Value of Help-Seeking," and (4) "Evolving Views on the Now and Tomorrow." The findings highlight the need for tailored interventions that address the unique challenges faced by suicide attempt survivors and emphasise the importance of collaborative efforts in suicide prevention.

Keywords: suicide attempt; suicide attempt survivor; suicide prevention; suicide recovery; suicide relapse

Suicide represents an agonising response to feelings of hopelessness and despair. For those who contemplate and ultimately attempt to take their own lives, it often appears to be the only escape from emotional turmoil and a perceived loss of purpose. Globally, suicide has become a pressing public health crisis. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), an estimated 703,000 people die by suicide each year, with countless others attempting to do so. However, the accuracy and comprehensiveness of suicide-related data remain limited due to underreporting and inconsistencies in documentation. In the Philippines, the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA, 2021) recorded 4,420 suicide-related deaths in 2020, making it the 25th leading cause of death that year. Despite these figures, concerns have been raised about the reliability of national suicide statistics due to potential measurement errors (Maligalig, n.d.).

The impact of suicide extends beyond the individual, affecting families, communities, and society at large (Shamsaei et al., 2020). While much attention is given to those who have died by suicide and the grief of their loved ones, the experiences of suicide attempt survivors remain underexplored. Their journey towards recovery is complex, involving emotional resilience, psychological rehabilitation, and the challenge of reintegration into daily life (Sokol et al., 2022). However, stigma surrounding suicide and mental health issues often discourages survivors from seeking help, further complicating efforts at recovery (Shaw et al., 2019). Despite the growing recognition of suicide prevention as a public health priority, only 38 countries have established national suicide prevention strategies, and few have made it a central focus of healthcare policy (WHO, 2023).

Suicide attempts are deeply personal and influenced by a range of psychological, social, and cultural factors. Yet, in the Philippine context, research has primarily focused on bereavement following a suicide loss or the factors that lead to an attempt, with little emphasis on survivors' recovery experiences. Existing literature also tends to centre on suicidal Filipino youth, leaving a significant gap in understanding the broader population of suicide attempt survivors. This study aims to address this gap by examining the first-hand experiences of Filipino adults recovering from suicide attempts, with a particular focus on relapse prevention. By amplifying survivors' voices, this research seeks to contribute to suicide prevention efforts and inform healthcare professionals, particularly nurses, on how to provide more targeted and effective support.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive phenomenological approach, which seeks to understand individuals' lived experiences by identifying universal essences within a phenomenon (Gasparyan, 2021). Researchers adhered to transcendental subjectivity, setting aside personal biases to authentically represent participants' experiences (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Participants and sampling

Purposive sampling was used to recruit 13 Filipino adults who had attempted suicide at least once and had not reattempted for a minimum of six months. Inclusion criteria ensured participants were Filipino-speaking, aged 18 or older, and residing in the Philippines. Individuals engaging solely in self-harm without suicidal intent were excluded. The six-month criterion was based on studies indicating heightened suicide risk within this period (Azcarate-Jiménez et al., 2019; Demesmaeker et al., 2021). Data saturation was reached after the 11th participant, with two additional interviews confirming no new insights.

Data collection

Semi-structured interviews allowed for flexibility while maintaining focus on the research aims (Mashuri et al., 2022). A validated 20-question guide was used, with expert consultation and

translation into Filipino to eliminate language barriers. Pilot interviews were conducted with three individuals (excluded from the main study) to ensure the effectiveness of the questions. Participants chose between face-to-face and online (Zoom/Google Meet) interviews, lasting 20 to 60 minutes, which were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim.

Data analysis

Data were analysed using Colaizzi's (1978) seven-step method, involving: (1) familiarisation with transcripts, (2) extraction of significant statements, (3) identification of meanings, (4) organisation into themes, (5) exhaustive description of the phenomenon, (6) identification of a central phenomenon, and (7) member checking for validation.

Ethical considerations

Approval was obtained from Dr. Yanga's Colleges, Inc. Ethics Review Board, ensuring adherence to ethical guidelines. Participants gave written and verbal informed consent, with the right to withdraw at any time. Pseudonyms were used to maintain anonymity, and data were handled in strict compliance with Philippine data privacy laws.

RESULTS

Table 1
 Demographic profile of the participants

Pseudonym	Age	Sex	Marital Status	Education Level	Occupation	Number of suicide attempt	How long ago the latest attempt was made	Attempt method
Tin	1	F	Single	University student	None	1	6 Months	Cutting the wrists
Love	1	F	Single	University student	None	1	1 year	Ingesting isopropyl alcohol
Alonica	9	M	Single	University student	None	2	2 years	Hanging (1) Ingesting liquid soap (1)
Anita	1	F	Single	University student	None	2	3 years	Hanging
Haru	0	M	Single	University student	None	4	3 years	Hanging (2) Suffocation (1) Holding breath (1)
Chanel	4	F	Single	University undergraduate	None	2	2 years	Cutting the wrists (1) Hanging (1)
Rainbow	4	F	Single	University graduate	None	4	1 year	Hanging (1) Overdosing of medication (1) Cutting the wrists (2)
Aya	1	F	Single	University student	None	2	6 years	Ingesting toilet bowl cleanser (1) Ingesting silica gel (1)
Perse	3	F	Single	University student	None	2	3 years	Hanging
Yanyan	9	F	Single	University student	Photography studio owner	6	5 years	Overdosing of medication (5) Cutting the wrists (1)
Aki	1	F	Single	University student	None	8	2 years	Cutting the wrists (7) Overdosing of medication (1)
Hinata	0	M	Single	University student	None	4	5 years	Cutting the wrists
Faith	9	F	Single	University student	None	1	1 year	Overdosing of medication

Table 1 summarises the demographic characteristics of the 13 participants, aged 19 to 24. The majority were female ($n = 10$), single, and had reached tertiary education, with 11 currently enrolled in a bachelor’s degree. Most ($n = 10$) had a history of multiple suicide attempts, indicating a deep familiarity with the phenomenon. Time since the last attempt varied from six months to six years. Suicide methods also differed, with some participants switching between methods, though wrist-cutting was the most common.

Loss of stability and control over self

Table 2

Theme clusters and formulated meanings under the emergent theme “Loss of Stability and Control Over Self”

Emergent Theme	Theme clusters	Formulated meanings
Loss of Stability and Control Over Self	Lack of self-awareness	Acting on suicidal ideation subconsciously Confusing depression with laziness Lack of self-care Limiting self-capability Impaired judgment
	Psychological suffering	Inability to control the impulse to hurt oneself Desire to end emotional pain Feeling burned out Perceived emotional invalidation by family Feeling alone Hearing voices Worthlessness Hopelessness Helplessness Overwhelming sadness Feeling pressure from the expectations of others Loss of interest Feeling like carrying the weight of the world on one’s own shoulders Feeling lost Feeling like everyone is against oneself Feeling disappointed with oneself
	Physiological impairment	Lack of energy Headache Frequent vomiting Feeling like dragging weight Loss of appetite

Table 2 presents the first emergent theme, “Loss of Stability and Control Over Self,” which explores the factors leading to a suicide attempt. The study distinguishes between two interconnected concepts: “loss of stability,” referring to a diminished ability to cope with life’s psychological and physiological demands, and “loss of control,” reflecting a perceived inability to influence circumstances. These losses contribute to feelings of uncertainty, insecurity, and powerlessness, often making suicide appear as the only means of escape or regaining agency.

Lack of self-awareness

Lack of self-awareness among suicidal individuals may manifest in their thoughts, feelings, or actions. While some suicide attempts are deliberate and premeditated, others may stem from a

subconscious desire to end one's life. Suicidality often goes unaddressed, as individuals may downplay or dismiss their distress as invalid or unworthy of help (Relajo-Howell, 2021). For instance, depression may be mistaken for laziness, making even basic self-care feel overwhelming. Furthermore, the intense preoccupation with suicidal thoughts and the urgency of the crisis can consume a person's energy and attention, leaving little capacity for self-care. Suicidal individuals often underestimate their own abilities, holding a persistent belief that they are inherently flawed and incapable of overcoming challenges. Suicide is ultimately an act of desperation – one driven by the overwhelming need to escape mental anguish. This distress severely impairs judgement, diminishing the ability to think clearly and make rational decisions, leading individuals to perceive suicide as the only viable option.

"I was shocked with myself. I did not realize that I was in the kitchen holding a knife with my right hand until my cell phone vibrated in my left hand. I did not know what I was doing there." (Tin)

"I would attempt suicide due to my clouded thoughts. I could not think straight. I could not think of positive thoughts, so I just wanted to do it." (Yanyan)

Psychological suffering

Psychological suffering encompasses a vast array of mental and emotional experiences that contribute to suicidal thoughts and behaviour. Survivors described their psychological state prior to their attempts differently, expressing their inability to control the impulse to hurt themselves, desire to end emotional pain, perceived emotional invalidation by their families, and loss of interest; as well as feelings of burnout, aloneness, worthlessness, hopelessness, helplessness, overwhelming sadness, pressure, burden, uncertainty, alienation, and self-disappointment. Not all suicidal people are secretive about their harmful thoughts. They may attempt to share their suicidal ideation with someone, only to meet judgmental reactions or be ignored; making them feel like no one can truly understand their pain. Some survivors reported hearing voices that resemble auditory hallucinations, which were either commands that lured them to commit suicide or derogatory remarks that others have previously told them.

"I could not think of anything else at the time but pain. I could only feel the pain. I did not think of anything else. I thought maybe this pain would be gone if I were to take my own life." (Chanel)

"There was like a voice whispering to my ears saying, 'Go ahead, hurt yourself. Go on because there is no other way out anyway.' It was like convincing me to commit suicide. There really is. It goes on." (Aki)

Physiological impairment

Physiological impairment focuses on the physicality of losing power over the self. In this study, it refers to physical symptoms that do not have an underlying organic cause and cannot be attributed to any known medical conditions, but instead originate from psychological suffering. This concept shows the interconnectedness of mental and physical health. Some survivors reported experiencing lack of energy, headache, frequent vomiting, feeling like dragging weight, and loss of appetite. Such physical manifestations can be highly distressing as these conditions exacerbate the feeling of loss of control over one's body.

"I would have headache. I would often vomit. I felt like I needed to drag my feet. They always hurt." (Tin)

“I didn’t feel like eating. It would last for three days.” (Aki)

Implications of the attempt to self and others

Table 3
 Theme clusters and formulated meanings under the emergent theme “Implications of the Attempt to Self and Others”

Emergent Themes	Theme Clusters	Formulated Meanings
Implications of the Attempt to Self and Others	Immediate emotional challenges	Questioning one’s own actions Guilt over perceived reaction of family to the attempt Shame about the attempt Fear of judgment Desire for others to change Expecting anger from family upon learning about the attempt Expecting others not to care Frustration about the failed attempt
	Impact of the attempt on relationships	Change in the attitude of family Feeling understood by family Receiving more attention from friends Feeling the emotional presence of family more Strengthened bond with family Increased introversion Cutting friends off Fixing relationship with family Reluctance to enter a romantic relationship Actions being questioned by family Perceived neglect by family

Table 3 shows the second emergent theme, “Implications of the Attempt to Self and Others.” It covers the inescapable consequences of an attempt not only for the emotional well-being of survivors but also the intricate dynamics of their relationships with the people around them, including their families, friends, and acquaintances.

Immediate emotional challenges

Surviving an attempt is a highly complicated situation. Considering suicide as the realization of the definite desire to end torment, immediate emotional challenges arise. As they confront the magnitude of their actions, survivors may question themselves and suddenly be confused as to why they proceeded with their attempts. They may feel responsible for their families’ emotional well-being and carry guilt about their predicted reaction of their families to their attempts, expecting anger or rejection. Due to the pervasive stigma attached to suicide, survivors automatically anticipate negative perceptions and reactions from their familial and social circles as many religions and cultures all over the world hold strong opinions about suicide, viewing it as a sin or a sign of weakness. Even some survivors believed suicide is a shameful deed and fear judgment by others with the idea of coming forward with their attempts. They could not accept that they reached the point where suicide became an option, such that the mere thought of attempting such an act feels unthinkable and embarrassing. A failed attempt could mean that survivors would have to put up with others’ unpleasant behaviour towards them, which can be perceived as a contributing factor to their distress, so they may wish for a change in the attitude of others to prevent future suicidal crises. On the contrary, survivors may continue to endure mental anguish and hopelessness, leaving them frustrated with their failed attempt.

“I was ashamed that I asked myself, ‘Why did I do that? Why did it cross my mind to do that?’” (Love)

“I was not happy about surviving my attempt because it meant that I would go through the same old routine. I am still alive. I am still here. They will take out their anger on me again. They can still hurt me and say hurtful words to me again.” (Aki)

Impact of the attempt on relationships

The aftermath of an attempt permeates through every facet of a survivor's life, such as their relationships with others. Mutual or differing perspectives on the attempt and suicide at large play an important role in shaping relationship dynamics, so much so that the attempt may either strain or strengthen relationships. Estrangement between survivors and the people whom they are close to happens as others often cannot empathize with survivors over the suicidal act that is considered contentious. Some survivors faced questioning and neglect by family members and opted to distance themselves from unsupportive friends and to refrain from forming romantic relationships, resulting in increased introversion. On the bright side, supportive responses can bridge connections and foster deeper and stronger bonds. The attempt can prompt a change in the attitudes of survivors' families, with family members becoming more aware and sensitive of their loved ones' mental health struggles. Following their attempts, many survivors noticed the increasing emotional presence of their families and their friends as they felt better understood by their families and received more attention from their friends.

“My mom and I disagreed when she found out that I attempted suicide. She discovered this because, with my first attempt, I left a letter for her and my sister. Although she had a different perspective on such a matter, we argued about why I would even consider such things when she thought our lives were going well. She felt like she had not failed me in any way.” (Perse)

“My parents are supportive. Some people say that my parents might antagonize me in situations like this, but my parents and relatives supported me. They were like, ‘We love you. Don’t do it again.’ It felt like they understood where I was coming from.” (Love)

Value of help-seeking

Table 4

Theme clusters and formulated meanings under the emergent theme “Value of Help-Seeking”

Emergent Themes	Theme Clusters	Formulated Meanings
Value of Help-Seeking	Barriers to help-seeking	Fear of side effects of psychotherapeutic drugs
		Financial constraints
		Fear of help-seeking being misinterpreted as an excuse to escape
		Self-isolation
		Unawareness of where to seek professional help
		Time constraints
		Fear of misdiagnosis
		Not wanting to cause additional emotional stress to family
		Stigma about psychiatric consultation and mental disorders
		Opposing views with family about help-seeking
	Facilitating factors for help-seeking	Personal desire to seek help
		Referral by friends
		Referral by peers
Professional help	Undergoing psychotherapy	
	Performing alternative coping strategies as advised by therapist	
	Taking psychotherapeutic drugs	
	Undergoing cognitive behavioral therapy	
	Watching informative videos about mental health	
Nonprofessional help	Support from friends	
	Journaling	
	Support from family	
	Renewed faith	
	Support from romantic partner	
	Using hobbies as a form of therapy	
	Having a me time	

Table 4 presents the third emergent theme, “Value of Help-Seeking.” It focuses on the survivors’ experiences as they sought and received help. While they may be aware of the significance of help-seeking in facilitating recovery and preventing reattempts, survivors may turn down help due to various reasons. This theme additionally stresses the factors that boost help-seeking behaviour, as well as the different sources of help and support networks available to survivors.

Barriers to help-seeking

As much as they acknowledged their need for help, survivors cited numerous barriers that made them initially reluctant to seek help. Mental health services usually come with a hefty price tag that discourages survivors with limited financial resources or inadequate insurance coverage. Survivors may either be forced to forgo necessary care or rely on less effective, potentially harmful alternatives. Mental health services that are available within reach may also be unbeknownst to survivors in the first place. Survivors had negative expectations concerning psychiatric consultation and how others would react to their help-seeking efforts. They may hesitate to start on medication therapy due to possible side effects of psychotherapeutic drugs, notably heightened suicidality from taking antidepressants, and fear misdiagnosis with the anxiety over the possibility of receiving incorrect treatment that may not alleviate or can worsen symptoms. The thought of being diagnosed with a mental health condition can be frightening enough for survivors as they may have internalized the discrimination against mentally ill individuals. Being labelled as “mentally ill” is deemed humiliating and degrading, which is why some survivors would rather not receive treatment than be the subject of ridicule as to save themselves from further psychological suffering. Mental health may not be even a priority for survivors against the demands of daily life, so they cannot find time to seek help. Some survivors admitted that they resorted to self-isolation because of the misconception that they are alone or that they should deal with their mental struggle independently, believing that

asking for help makes them a burden to others. The society largely maintains negative views towards help-seeking, which they may misconstrue to be as an excuse to escape obligations in school or work and simply denounce as unnecessary.

“I really tried to help myself...I tried to go to a psychiatrist. I looked for psychiatrists. I found one in Santa Maria, but I could not afford a consult with my allowance because one session costs ₱2,500.00 or ₱1,500.00, I think.” (Aki)

“I thought I was alone. This prevented me from communicating my thoughts and feelings. People around me would have been aware otherwise. I was wrong.” (Alonica)

Facilitating factors for help-seeking

Motivators for help-seeking behaviour are categorized in this study as “facilitating factors for help-seeking.” These elements may include a range of influences, such as personal resilience, encouragement from trusted individuals, and social support networks. Survivors who possess intrinsic motivation are more likely to actively participate in therapy, adhere to treatment plans, and adopt healthier coping strategies. In addition to their personal desire to seek help, survivors credited their friends and peers for facilitating referrals to mental health services.

“Perhaps when I realized it myself, I really wanted to move forward. I wanted to get out of that situation. I did not want to stay stuck there.” (Aya)

“I have a friend who is a psychology student. They recommended that I undergo psychotherapy.” (Tin)

Professional help

Professional help is consequential for survivors so they can process their experiences, thoughts, and emotions. Mental health professionals guide survivors as they deal with their situation, helping them identify underlying mental health issues that contributed to their attempts and develop healthy coping strategies. Additionally, mental health professionals can provide a sense of safety and validation, which can be particularly helpful for survivors who feel stigmatized or ashamed about their attempts.

“I had CBT (cognitive behavioural therapy) monthly. During every check-up, the doctor would follow a structure so I could verbalize my internalized thoughts. The therapy was beneficial because before, I had a lot of experiences wherein I could not correctly process my thoughts. After all, they are traumatic. I verbalized them to my doctor, and we processed them in a way like, ‘Are we going to let go of this? What are we going to do about this?’ My life felt like it finally had direction.” (Love)

“...they counselled me. It was the only thing that gave me comfort.” (Hinata)

Nonprofessional Help

In addition to availing mental health services, survivors can benefit from various forms of nonprofessional help. In this study, nonprofessional help includes informal support networks like family, friends, romantic partners, and faith, as well as personal efforts such as journaling, hobbies, and having a “me” time. Some survivors even consider nonprofessional help alone as already helpful in coping with their attempts.

“I think the biggest help were from my friends because I open up to them whenever I feel overwhelmed.” (Faith)

“Because I love music and arts, I use them as a form of therapy to forget my bad habits. I make them my outlet.” (Rainbow)

Evolving views on the now and tomorrow

Table 5

Theme clusters and formulated meanings under the emergent theme “Evolving Views on the Now and Tomorrow”

Emergent Themes	Theme Clusters	Formulated Meanings
Evolving Views on the Now and Tomorrow	Current feelings about the attempt	Coexisting paradoxical feelings about the attempt
		Viewing the failed attempt as a chance to start over
		Using the attempt as a motivation to overcome current challenges
	Current feelings about life post-attempt	Disbelief in choosing to commit an attempt
		Viewing the failed attempt as a turning point
		Viewing the attempt as an overcome challenge
		Finding life to be more difficult
		Finding life to be more meaningful
		Feeling hopeful
	Realizations from the attempt	Finding life as an exciting adventure
		Finding peace
		Finding a renewed sense of self
Realising the need for a stronger sense of self		
Appreciating the beauty of life more		
Learning that emotional healing is possible		
Learning to verbalize thoughts and feelings		
Gaining a new perspective in life		
Learning to live life for good		
Realising the need to become emotionally stronger		
Protective factors against suicide	Developing empathy	
	Realising that suicide is not the answer	
	Realising the opportunity to move forward	
	Learning to cherish loved ones more	
	Learning to embrace life as a one-time chance	
	Learning self-love	
	Realising that there are people who care	
	Learning from mistakes	
	Thinking about family	
Idolizing celebrities		
Hobbies and interests		
Finding purpose		
Prioritizing self over others		
Avoiding unwanted people		
Having supportive friends		
Finding companionship in pets		
Feeling loved by romantic partner		

Table 5 reflects the fourth and last emergent theme “Evolving Views on the Now and Tomorrow.” In this final aspect of the suicide attempt experience, the researchers uncover the changing perspectives of survivors, specifically probing into how they find meaning in their attempt and their current life. It further discusses the lessons the survivors learned from their attempts, as well as their motivations to live and not reattempt suicide.

Current feelings about the attempt

Examining survivors’ current feelings about their attempts evaluates how they give meaning to it, allowing for a deeper exploration of the lasting impact of their attempts on their emotional well-

being. Coexisting paradoxical feelings of regret and frustration may persist. However, most survivors expressed positive views towards their attempts. They now see their attempts as a turning point, a chance to start over, a source of motivation, and an overcome challenge itself.

“It depends. There are times when I wish my attempt was successful. There are also times when I was like, ‘[profanity], what was I doing then?’” (Tin)

“For me, my attempts were a turning point in my life. And it is just funny now like it does not bother me anymore when I think about it, or like now that we are talking about it. It is like nothing to me now. I am just rethinking how I dealt with it, but it does not bother me anymore.” (Haru)

Current feelings about life post-attempt

This theme cluster reveals how the attempt possibly reshaped life’s course for survivors. Survivors had varying sentiments and reflections regarding their current feelings about their life post-attempt, implying that the trajectory post-attempt is not the same for all survivors. Surviving an attempt cannot guarantee relief from psychological suffering. Even in the long run, the aftermath of an attempt may involve ongoing emotional turmoil. In contrast, survivors may find hope as they progress through their journey to recovery, holding onto the belief that things will get better and that they have the power to surmount anything that life throws their way. They may also find a renewed sense of self, a perspective that translates into the aftermath of their attempts being a transformative phase. Some survivors shared that they have finally found their life to be more meaningful and exciting, learning to make peace with their attempts.

“It is more difficult because I do not know when it will happen again. Then, I worry, “What if it happens soon? What if I succumb to my thoughts?” This is why it is scarier when you attempt suicide. Then, after that, I would think, “What if it happens again?” Then, I would fail to resist my thoughts and give up.” (Tin)

“Now, I believe life is perhaps a very exciting adventure. But at the same time, there are the unknowns that are hard to grasp. I am somewhat fond of adventure. I like to travel to different places. So now, I am just looking forward to the thrills and happiness that life would bring me, and I will not dwell on the sad things anymore.” (Haru)

Realisations from the attempt

As the experience of attempting suicide meant differently to them, survivors have made various realizations from their attempts. These essences evince that there is something to learn from their attempts, which encourages survivors to push through with their lives. Surviving an attempt can be an unexpected pivotal moment. Since their attempts, survivors have become more appreciative of the beauty of life. The failed attempt can be a wake-up call for endless possibilities and opportunities that life has in store for them, so they have since committed to moving forward and living life to the fullest and for good. As they rediscover themselves along the way, survivors can regain power over their thoughts and learn to love themselves more than ever by accepting their flaws as humans. Most importantly, survivors concluded that suicide is not the answer and that there are always alternatives, accessible sources of support, and reasons to hold onto hope, even in the darkest times.

“The most important thing I learned is that suicide is not the answer to problems. There are much better ways to overcome this. It might be difficult. But once you surpass it, for me, it is worth it to stay in this world.” (Perse)

“After the attempt, I realized that there are people who love me. Some people worry about me. It was like my world brightened. After my fourth attempt, I realized that people love me. Some people understand me. After the attempt, I started to open myself up. I started with my mom. I learned to express my thoughts so that they are aware, too.” (Rainbow)

Protective factors

In this study, protective factors are elements or conditions that promote resilience and reduce suicidality among survivors. In other words, these are the factors that motivate survivors to go on with life and not reconsider suicide. Survivors mentioned several protective factors, which are family, celebrity idols, hobbies and interests, finding purpose, prioritizing oneself, avoiding unwanted people, friends, and pets.

“Of course, my family. I am making it up to them. I will do my best to repay them.” (Love)

“When I am feeling down, I try to remember my reasons for living. I want to finish my studies. I want to work. I want to earn money. I want to live independently. I think about my future aims in life. I still need to accomplish them.” (Anita)

Learning to LIVE Again

Figure 1

Illustration of the central phenomenon “Learning to LIVE Again”

The narratives of the informants revealed a recurrent pattern of events surrounding a suicide attempt as seen in Figure 1. The illustration displays the uphill path that suicide attempt survivors navigate in the hopes of finally recovering from their attempts and effectively preventing reattempts. The silhouette represents the suicide attempt survivor to imply that suicide has no face and knows no boundaries, affecting individuals of any age, gender, race, and socioeconomic status. Four chronological aspects that comprise the phenomenon of surviving an attempt serve as the major themes of this study, forming the acronym “LIVE”: (1) “Loss of Stability and Control Over Self,” (2) “Implications of the Attempt to Self and Others,” (3) “Value of Help-Seeking,” and (4) “Evolving Views on the Now and Tomorrow.”

The cave symbolises “Loss of Stability and Control Over Self.” The darkness and enclosure of the cave alludes to the uncertainty that accompanies the difficulty to recover power over one’s life. As a suicidal person feels trapped in their circumstances, escape seems impossible. Suffocating feelings of

hopelessness and helplessness ensue, provoking the urge to end their own life. Unable to hold out against inner turmoil, the individual attempts suicide.

The unintentional survival of an attempt triggers a whole other myriad of complex emotions that may include guilt, shame, and frustration and affects the attempter's relationships with significant others and within their social circle, hence the emergent theme "Implications of the Attempt to Self and Others." The weight of these consequences on the suicide attempt survivor is portrayed in the image by the falling boulders.

The lighthouse is a metaphor for the "Value of Help-Seeking." Like a lighthouse for travellers, various support systems can be a refuge for the suicide attempt survivor. The lighthouse is positioned high on the mountain to signify the idea that help is available yet difficult to access for the suicide attempt survivor.

As the suicide attempt survivor approaches the summit, the radiance of the sun becomes progressively perceptible as symbolic of the emergent theme "Evolving Views on the Now and Tomorrow." The light beams hope that guides the suicide attempt survivor towards emotional healing and growth.

Climbing the way up is an intimidating and daunting challenge. In spite of the arduous journey towards recovery, each step forward is already a sign of triumph of resilience and perseverance over despair. The rate of progress varies among suicide attempt survivors as signified by how quickly or slowly they ascend their way up and how they might stop in the middle of the road at some point. Just as a two-way street and the likelihood of going downhill being much easier than going uphill, they might return to their old ways and commit reattempts as further connoted by the footsteps.

Combining all the emergent themes in this study, the researchers identified a central phenomenon, aptly termed "Learning to LIVE Again." It suggests that individuals who attempted and survived a suicide attempt undergo a transformative process. As suicide attempt survivors take such stride, they soon learn to rediscover their sense of identity, reframe their experiences and perspectives, and redefine their values and goals. Ultimately, they become empowered to embrace life. Relearning how to live does not end with mere survival and existence. It is to find joy, purpose, and hope in living despite all odds.

DISCUSSION

In recent times, the world's view on suicide has evolved with a growing recognition of suicide as a health emergency. In the realm of research, considerable work has been undertaken to expand current knowledge about suicide. Nonetheless, previous research efforts mostly focused on suicidality and familial grief over the loss of a loved one to suicide, whereas understanding of experiences with a failed suicide attempt remains scarce. In this study, the researchers investigated the lived realities of suicide attempt survivors to form a vivid and comprehensive portrayal of their journey as they commit an attempt, pursue recovery, and fight the ingrained desire to end their lives. As a result of data analysis, a total of four emergent themes and 13 theme clusters were extracted.

The events that precede an attempt varied among survivors. As articulated by Shamsaei et al. (2020), suicide is multifactorial and rarely results from a single cause. In general, the survivors' disabling encounters prior to their attempts fall under the first emergent theme, "Loss of Stability and Control Over Self." This phrase was coined to describe how the demands of life can overwhelm individuals to the point of failure to cope and preserve overall well-being, inevitably leading them to attempt suicide. Contrary to stereotypical belief, suicide is not always planned, neither consciously done. As a matter of fact, acting on suicidal ideation has been thought as a consequence of impulsivity (Brokke et al., 2022) and impaired judgment (Wang et al., 2021). In this sense, suicide

indeed is not a choice. Alternatively speaking, people who committed suicide might not have decided to take their own life out of free will. Attempting suicide means that they surrender in the battle against unfathomable suffering of the mind and psyche as alternative options to suicide failed, and, for them, suicide is the only solution to their problems. The survivors provided varying descriptions about their psychological state before their attempts. Likewise, researchers in the past dwelled on the mental and emotional landscape of suicidal individuals, reflecting themes that arose in this study, namely exhaustion (Oh et al., 2023), mental pain (Shamsaei et al., 2020), emotional neglect (Zhong et al., 2024), aloneness (Shoib et al., 2023), and academic stress (Okechukwu et al., 2022). In their studies, these were cited as contributing factors to suicidal thoughts and behaviour. Furthermore, feelings of worthlessness, hopelessness, and helplessness were identified among some survivors, echoing Beck's (1967) cognitive triad of depression. Aside from Beck's (1967) cognitive triad of depression, two other symptoms that are part of the diagnostic criteria for major depressive disorder emerged from the survivors' statements: persistently depressed mood and loss of interest (American Psychiatric Association, 2022). Untreated or inadequately treated depression is the most common cause of suicide (Andrew, 2022). In coherence with a recent study by Toyohara et al. (2021), another notable finding in the current study is the presence of voices that are similar to auditory hallucinations, which either command suicidal people to commit suicide or are negative remarks that they have been told by others. According to some survivors, suicidal ideation also manifested as deviations in their physical health. Previous researchers supported that changes in physical activity levels (Michael et al., 2020) and appetite (Xu et al., 2020) are medical symptoms related to suicidal ideation.

Since the survivors were determined to end their own lives, surviving an attempt is not necessarily a relieving experience. Confronted with an unexpected turn of situation, the failed attempt brings forth negative feelings. Exploring such emotions is believed to be a distinctive aspect of this study. Survivors suffer from a unique kind of grief immediately after an attempt, possibly contemplating the question, "What now?" The emotional conflicts following an attempt also differed among survivors with the emergence of contradicting statements that generally conveyed either remorse or frustration. In addition, the researchers discovered that an attempt can positively or negatively impact the survivors' personal and social relationships. Some survivors felt that their families became more perceptive and emotionally present and that their attempts brought them closer to their families. These positive relationship outcomes can be attributed to increased perceived salience among family members towards underlying mental health issues. On the flip side, families are not always discerning when it comes to making sense of the suicidal act by their loved ones, possibly brought by the influence of societal attitudes towards suicide and a lack of awareness about mental health. Moreover, other survivors lamented that the attempt affected their social life in a way that they are still unready to enter new friendly and romantic relationships. Altogether, the effects of a failed attempt gave rise to the second emergent theme, "Implications of the Attempt to Self and Others."

As they strive to move forward and seek to regain their will to live, survivors require tremendous and consistent care. Despite the promising benefits of various forms of help for survivors, getting the necessary support is another challenge of its own. Survivors may not have adequate monetary resources to cover for consultation, admission, and treatment fees, a finding that is in congruence with past studies by Heinsch et al. (2020) and Stunden et al. (2020). Mental health services can be too costly for survivors to refuse clinical attention or resort to other options that are subpar or even unsafe. Along with financial concerns, social stigma against mental health conditions is a common barrier to help-seeking (Shaw et al., 2019). Having internalized this long-standing stigma, survivors are inclined to adopt the public's misconceptions about suicide and psychiatric treatment. They may believe their struggles are not real but a sign of weakness or personal failure. They may also fear being diagnosed with a mental disorder due to the negative societal connotations attached to being "mentally ill." On a positive note, survivors acknowledge their need for help. Help-seeking behaviour should be encouraged among survivors because with the innate determination to seek help,

increased compliance to treatment regimen and optimal mental health outcomes are better ensured. Available help for survivors exists in different modes, which can be classified into two main types: professional and nonprofessional help. “Professional help” is a unifying term for all forms of interventions and services that are rendered by mental health professionals. Consulting a mental health professional can be useful in the diagnosis and treatment of mental illnesses that intensify suicidality, such as affective and psychotic disorders (Szmajda et al., 2023). Meanwhile, sources of support other than mental health professionals fall under “nonprofessional help.” Most survivors found informal help from their friends and their faith. Other possible sources of nonprofessional help are family, romantic partners, and personal efforts that include journaling, hobbies, and having a “me time.” For some survivors, nonprofessional help alone can be enough to help them cope with the aftermath of their attempts. All these measures have been enumerated by Nurdianto and Subandi (2021) as “sources of psychological help.” The survivors’ encounters with help-seeking led to the third emergent theme, “Value of Help-Seeking.”

Survivors’ attitude towards their attempts and life gradually changes with time. This shift substantiates the fourth and final emergent theme, “Evolving Views on the Now and Tomorrow.” The informants of this study have not reattempted suicide for at least six months following their most recent attempt. Having spent their time into recovery at varying lengths may explain for their diverse perceptions. Survivors’ prospects were observed to improve the longer they can resist the urge to commit reattempts. Nevertheless, a longer period of survival cannot guarantee more favourable mental health outcomes. Survivors may remain suicidal, and suicidal individuals are assumed to fluctuate between having the wish to live and the wish to die (Bryan, 2020). The coexistence of such conflicting feelings is called suicide ambivalence. Suicide ambivalence is not limited to the immediate period after an attempt as it may persist over time (Höller et al., 2024). Although negative feelings may still occur, almost all the survivors considered themselves recovered and demonstrated a more positive outlook on their attempts and their current life. The failed attempt may mark a watershed in survivors’ lives. From confusion to shame and frustration, survivors later find meaning in their attempts and become more forgiving of themselves. Overcoming suicidality is a milestone, empowering them to take another chance at life, turn their lives around, and eventually learn that suicide is not and should never be the answer. Many survivors shared that their families are the most important reason that they chose living over dying. This finding resonates with Filipino family culture that gives paramount value and importance to close-knit family ties. Finding purpose, friends, prioritizing oneself, pets, hobbies and interests, avoiding unwanted people, romantic partners, and idolized celebrities are also protective factors against suicide.

CONCLUSION

Suicide is not a rational choice but rather motivated by a blind desire for relief, thinking that life feels even worse than death. For suicidal ideation to become a reality speaks volumes for intolerable and seemingly endless pain that makes one lose sight of any hope left for the future. With the clear intent of taking their own life, surviving a suicide attempt entails reliving their suffering. Survivors are bound to face emotional challenges following their attempts, initially confronted with confusion, shame, or frustration. The attempt transcends beyond human individuality, crossing and altering the dynamics within survivors’ personal and social relationships. Some bonds may strengthen, while others may experience strain or even breakdown. Survivors are in dire need of help from mental health professionals and people within their inner circles who can walk with them as they navigate the tumultuous road towards reclaiming their will to live. The journey of suicide attempt survivors is not linear as they may go back and forth between wanting to live and wishing to die. Notwithstanding, with adequate support and guidance, suicide attempt survivors can emerge with realized potential for resilience, growth, and hope, ultimately learning to live again.

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